

Promotion of Urinary Continence among Stroke Survivors

Abayomi Lawal, DNP, RN, PHN; Deanna Jung DNP, APRN, AGACNP-BC; Penny Weismuller, DrPH, RN

Purpose

Improve health outcomes for stroke survivors with urinary incontinence (UI) by

- Developing and implementing an evidence-based guideline (EBG) to address gaps in the management and treatment of UI.
- Educating and empowering nurses

Background

- UI is an unwanted urine leakage or retention
- Stroke may hinder the central neurologic pathway for voiding
- 60% of stroke survivors suffer UI
- The rate of UI is increasing despite rehabilitation efforts to treat and manage it
- Harmful effects of UI: Sepsis, multi-therapy disruption, and discharge problem
- Types of UI: Stress, urge, overflow, functional, mixed, and/or transient
- Gaps in documentation, treatment, or knowledge among nursing staff

A Three Step Approach

Supporting Framework

Facilitator Focus and Activity

What the Facilitator Looks at
What the Facilitator Does

Methods

- Innovation: Promotion of urinary continence (PUC) guideline for stroke survivors
- Recipients: Nursing staff and stroke survivors
- Context: Setting of the QI project and factors that have significant influence on the setting
 - Inner Context: 46-bed stroke unit of inpatient rehabilitation facility and stakeholders
 - Outer Context: CARF, Joint Commission, and Association of Rehabilitation Nurses
- Facilitation: PUC, Stakeholders buy-in, Education, Implementation and Evaluation
- Inclusion criteria: Functional independence measure bladder score (FIMBS) of ≤ 4 upon admission and length of stay ≥ 6 days
- Pre and post PUC patients' FIMBSs change was calculated using SPSS version 24.0

Results

- 57 (> 90%) nursing staff educated on PUC
- Sample sizes: Pre (N = 84) & post (N=82)
- Pre FIMBS mean 1.31, Post FIMBS mean 1.72
- 31% increase in the post-PUC FIMBS
- Post FIMBS mean $t(2.32) = 81, p = 0.023$ when compared with pre FIMBS mean score
- Steady monthly increases in FIMBS indicated improvement in continence post PUC implementation

Limitation

- Float nursing staff to the unit
- Charting via hard copy versus online
- Convenience sampling utilized

Implication for Practice

- The result indicated EBG improved urinary continence among stroke survivors
- Ongoing education required for sustainability of positive outcomes of EBG
- EBG must be flexible to meet new challenges

Conclusion

- PUC led to changes in practice and increased scores in FIMBS
- Resulted in 31% increase in urinary continence rate
- Increase in awareness of EBG/EBP among inpatient and rehabilitation units
- Further studies are needed to address the modified pelvic floor muscle exercises used to manage UI in nurse-driven interventions

For More Information

Abayomi Lawal, DNP, RN, PHN

Email: lawalyomi2002@yahoo.com